

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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THE ROLE OF TURKON KHOTUN IN THE LIFE OF THE KHWAREZMSHAHID STATE

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Abstract: in this article as a woman of Takash in the life of the Khorezmshah state, which existed on the territory of our homeland in the Middle Ages. As part of a broader analysis of the role of Alouddin Khwarezmshah's parent Turkon khotun in state affairs, we will dwell on the case when he studied historical sources from the Middle Ages and the present.

Key words: Khwarazmshahs, Takash, Turkon khotun, Bartold, Juzjani, Kipchak, Alouddin Muhammad, Urganch, Samarkand, Jaloliddin Manguberdi, Qutbiddin Özlüqshoh, Oychechak, Qorahani, Mughals, Genghis Khan, Khwarazm, state.

XORAZMSHOHLAR DAVLATI HAYOTIDA TURKON XOTUNNING O'RNI.

Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada takash ayoli sifatida o'rta asrlarda vatanimiz hududida mavjud bo'lgan Xorazmshohlar davlati hayotida. Alouddin Xorazmshohning ota-onasi Turkon xotunning davlat ishlarida tutgan o'rnini kengroq tahlil qilish doirasida uning o'rta asrlar va hozirgi davrga oid tarixiy manbalarni o'rgangan holiga to'xtalamiz.

Kalit so'zlar: Xorazmshohlar, Takash, Turkon xotun, Bartold, Juzjoni, Qipchoq, Alouddin Muhammad, Urganch, Samarqand, Jaloliddin Manguberdi, Qutbiddin O'zlug'shoh, Oychechak, Qoraxoni, Mug'ullar, Chingizxon, Xorazm, davlat.

РОЛЬ ТУРКОН-ХОТУНА В ЖИЗНИ ГОСУДАРСТВА ХВАРЕЗМШАХИДОВ

Аннотация: в данной статье рассматривается женщина Такаша в жизни государства Хорезмшахов, существовавшего на территории нашей Родины в Средние века. В рамках более широкого анализа роли родителя Алоуддина Хорезмшаха Туркона хотуна в государственных делах остановимся на случае, когда он изучал исторические источники средневековья и современности.

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Ключевые слова: Хорезмшахи, Такаш, Тюркон хотун, Бартольд, Джуджани, Кипчак, Алоуддин Мухаммад, Ургенч, Самарканд, Джалолиддин Мангуберди, Кутбиддин Озлюксох, Ойчечак, Горахани, Моголы, Чингисхан, Хорезм, государство.

Takash enters into an alliance with the Kipchaks and marries Turkon khotun, the daughter of the Khan of the Kipchaks. The famous historian V. According to Bartold v, Turconus was a khotun hemp seed. Juzzhoni, on the other hand, is cited as having been the daughter of Kipchak Kadir Khan in sources. Along with Turkon khotun, The Bayat seed of the Kipchaks, many Turkic people, military, also entered Khwarezm. Turkon khotun later became their powerful patron, while a Turkic – military layer also emerged in the state.

Historical sources claim that Turkon khotunni was an ambitious, hypocritical and vengeful woman for power. She was the Scorpio of the three great commanders and rulers, simultaneously the wife of Khwarezmshah Takash, mother of Khwarezmshah Alouddin Muhammad and grandmother of Sultan Jalaliddin. Its tugal derivative, on the other hand, was fully manifested during the later reign of Sultan Muhammad (R.1200-1220). In the defense of the city of Urgench in 1204, he was able to show himself. Turkon khotun armed the entire population of the city and ordered the organization of the defense of the city, and The Defenders of the ring missed the city. In 1210, the Karakhanid captain Sultan Usman was married to his grandson Khan Sultan. By order of Turkon khotun, Sultan Uthman was held in the Khwarezmshah Palace for a year without being released anywhere. If two instructions came from the Queen and the Sultan about one case, then they decided on their date and followed the next in all countries.

The Sultan soon declared Samarkand his capital and settled in the same city in 1218. It should be noted that in the khwarezmshah dynasty, a unique diarchy had developed – that is, a system of hypocrisy. Although Sultan Muhammad Khwarazmshah was considered the absolute ruler, the owner of a powerful state, in fact, he was completely subordinate to his mother Turkon khotun Izmi. In many cases, the Sultan's decrees were also canceled by his mother. The Sultan would never oppose his mother, and the case was pointed out by historian an-nasawi in the following way by attributing it to two reasons - “firstly, his appreciation of his mother's affection for her, and secondly, that all the emirs of the country were from his mother's seed”.

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Turkon khotun had the nickname "World governor", and his personal seal (tughro)bore the inscription: "Ismat ud-Dunya vad-din the Great Turkon Princess niso al-olamiyn ("the world and its purity, The Great Turkon, Queen of the women of the universe"). Turkon khotun was a permanent resident of the capital Gurganj, had his own palace, huge estates. The Sultan would present the wealthiest territories in the occupied lands, the best booty, to his mother. The queen personally manages the affairs of the kingdom, finances, makes decrees in the appropriate way, monitors the appointment of Viceroy and officials, etc.

Turkon appointed kenja Qutbiddin Özlükshah as crown prince, not khotun Jaloliddin Manguberdi. Because Turkon, the mother of Özlükshah, was a descendant of khotun. Turkon khotun did not like Oychechak, the mother of another seed, Prince Jalaliddin. Individuals who were occasionally captured or held hostage at the direction of Turkon khotun, former governors, were executed. The governors acted as far as they knew, and there was no clear system of collecting taxes. It was common to build any Road, Bridge, Fort and other structures (suhra giriftan) with Hashar road. When the state was in a state of tension, there was not much confidence left for the residents. Some provincial governors would personally submit to Turkon khotun and act as they knew. Turkon khotun, the parent of Sultan Muhammad, had a strong connection with the Kipchak Warlords, The Supreme Warlords of the army, always supporting them as he belonged to that tribe. Commanders, army chiefs, ministers, governors were appointed in large part by his permission and direction, which, in turn, were primarily subordinate to Turkon khotun.

Khorezmshah's mother Turkon khotun was in fact considered a first-class person in the state, whose motto was inscribed on the seal of "e'tasantu Billohi Vahda" (i.e., "I seek refuge from God alone"), and with this seal on the ruler's decree, his decree was considered important if he signed first.

Turkon khotun thus corresponded with many rulers-within them was Hatto, the Arab caliph. Genghis Khan had Khwarazm taken to his court after the conquest. Turkon khotun lived in Genghis Palace for the rest of his life. There may be two reasons why he was not killed. The first reason was that in the Legation of the Mongols were forbidden to kill women, especially noble women. It is unlikely that the second reason was precisely from the Turkic tribe, and that the emeks, which also included the Mongols, did not want Turkon to die.

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